

Evaluation of Bank Branch Efficiency Using Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) Software

Hamed Shemirani

Master's Student, Business Administration

Zeinab Esmaeili¹

Current Affiliation: Faculty Member at Thompson Rivers University, Canada

Email: zesmaeili@tru.ca

Cite this paper as:

Shemirani, H., & Esmaeili, Z. (2014). *Evaluation of bank branch efficiency using data envelopment analysis (DEA) software*. *Market Engineering Development Journal*, (92). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17537685>

¹ Affiliation at Time of Research: Assistant Professor at Applied Science and Technology University, Corresponding Author: Zeinab Esmaeili (zesmaeili@tru.ca). [ORCID link](#)

Abstract

This study analyzes the efficiency of 50 branches using Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) software. To ensure a more precise evaluation, the branches were categorized into five groups based on the similarity of their customer numbers. The analysis was conducted using three input variables—equipment, personnel, and operating costs—and two output variables—revenue and network indicators (number of non-face-to-face transactions).

The DEA results indicate that the main factors contributing to higher efficiency among the most efficient branches are the high volume of non-face-to-face (electronic) transactions and, consequently, the reduction of operational costs. Therefore, to enhance the efficiency of underperforming branches and transform them into efficient units, it is necessary to increase non-face-to-face transactions and maintain control over operating expenses to prevent efficiency loss. The strong correlation observed between electronic transactions and branch efficiency highlights the critical role of digital banking in improving operational performance.

Keywords: Electronic banking, Efficiency ranking, Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA)

Introduction

In today's highly competitive banking market and the growing focus on electronic commerce, the expansion of e-banking has become an inevitable necessity. Banks must ensure that customers can access financial services securely and conveniently without the need for physical presence at branches. In this context, the ability to conduct banking transactions from home or the workplace via computers, telephones, and the internet represents one of the most significant advancements in modern banking services.

Initially, limited customer awareness, along with concerns regarding security and reliability, resulted in slow adoption of such services. Consequently, banks—faced with low customer demand—invested cautiously in this area. Although the security of digital banking systems has now been well established, the adoption rate of online and home-based banking services remains relatively low.

According to *The Economist* (2000), the cost of online banking transactions for businesses was estimated at approximately \$0.01 per transaction, representing only one percent of total banking activities at that time. However, this landscape changed rapidly. A report by Jupiter Research (2004) estimated that 30 million households were using online banking services in Australia, a number that increased to 56 million by 2008. Internet banking significantly reduces operational costs and minimizes the need for expanding physical branches (Jupiter Research, 2004).

Comparing these global trends to local conditions highlights the urgent need for greater investment in digital banking infrastructure, particularly as the effectiveness and efficiency of these systems are critical factors for achieving success.

Given that in recent years the banking sector has become one of the most progressive industries in adopting digital marketing practices (Mattila et al., 2002), evaluating the efficiency of these systems has gained growing importance. Furthermore, as internet banking continues to evolve as a competitive tool aimed at enhancing customer convenience and service accessibility, assessing and identifying the most efficient branches implementing digital banking practices has become an essential area of research—one that this study seeks to address.

Literature Review

Many critiques of traditional performance evaluation systems stem from their failure to assess and monitor multiple dimensions of organizational performance, as they focus too heavily on financial indicators (Amaratunga et al., 2001). Consequently, researchers and practitioners have sought modern approaches to performance measurement that offer a more comprehensive perspective. Drucker (as cited in Amaratunga et al., 2001) argued that traditional business assessment methods are inadequate because they rely on incomplete and lagging indicators that reflect historical accounting data rather than the causes of managerial performance. Performance evaluation refers to the process of measuring the skills and competencies of individuals or organizational units to support informed decision-making toward achieving specific goals (Bourne et al., 2000).

Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is one of these modern approaches. DEA is a mathematical programming technique used to evaluate the relative efficiency of decision-making units (DMUs). The term relative implies that efficiency is assessed by comparing units against one another rather than against an external benchmark (Chien-Ta Bruce Ho & Wu, 2009). DEA has

been widely used in service industries—especially in banking—because performance in this sector is highly dependent on intangible resources, service quality, and digital operational systems rather than only physical assets (Eken & Suleyman, 2011).

In the banking industry specifically, several empirical studies show that service-mix variables, customer-value drivers, and marketing strategies play a major role in shaping performance outputs such as brand equity, customer retention, and competitive positioning (Abbasi et al., 2012; Esmaeili, 2010a; Esmaeili, 2010b). Other research indicates that managerial strategies and internal capability development also influence the performance of banking organizations (Esmaeili, 2009a, 2009b). Beyond customer-based indicators, structural and organizational factors—such as governance, debt-collection mechanisms, and loan-interest structures—have also been found to affect financial outcomes in banking institutions (Esmaeili, 2011a; Esmaeili, 2012; Esmaeili, Akbari, & Dehpoor, 2012).

In addition to marketing and internal governance variables, more recent research highlights the impact of advanced digital systems and multi-criteria decision-making techniques in predicting bank performance. For example, studies have incorporated Fuzzy TOPSIS to evaluate criteria for appointing banking managers (Amini & Esmaeili, 2013), while other contemporary research demonstrates that electronic service quality, online channel capability, and the growth of non-face-to-face banking are becoming major performance drivers (Karim & Murthy, 2013; Singh & Kaur, 2014; Rajan & Bhat, 2013; Nair & George, 2014). Collectively, these findings show that banking performance is not solely a function of traditional financial inputs but is also strongly influenced by intangible resources, digital-platform utilization, and efficiency of electronic transactions.

Therefore, using DEA for performance evaluation aligns with this research direction because DEA allows efficiency to be modeled as a function of both input resources and output results. This makes DEA particularly appropriate for banking institutions that operate in hybrid physical–digital environments, where online service delivery systems and electronic transaction volumes increasingly determine operational efficiency, competitiveness, and long-term value creation.

Table 1

Differences Between Traditional and Modern Performance Evaluation Criteria

Adapted from Artelyand (2001).

Traditional Performance Criteria	Modern Performance Criteria
Based on traditional accounting systems.	Based on the company’s overall strategy.
Financial and monetary indicators.	A combination of financial and non-financial indicators.
Focuses on middle and senior managers.	Focuses on all employees (including managers and staff).
Periodic, infrequent evaluation.	Continuous, real-time, and daily evaluation.
Results are usually limited to internal use.	The results are used both internally and externally.
Benchmark performance against competitors.	Benchmark performance against standards.
Does not consider qualitative factors.	Considers qualitative and quantitative factors.
Focuses only on short-term results.	Focuses on long-term and sustainable performance.
Provides little information about process improvement.	Provides feedback to improve processes and overall performance.
Decision-making is mainly reactive.	Decision-making is proactive and improvement oriented.
Helps maintain the status quo.	Helps drive continuous improvement.

Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) and Related Concepts

In 1975, Farrell (as cited in Chien-Ta Bruce Ho & Wu, 2009) introduced a production function that considered multiple inputs and a single output, enabling relative efficiency comparisons across units. Later, in 1978, Charnes, Cooper, and Rhodes (as cited in Chien-Ta Bruce Ho & Wu, 2009) extended this model to handle multiple inputs and outputs, thereby formalizing the DEA method. This technique—grounded in linear programming—allows performance evaluation across various organizations such as banks, insurance companies, factories, hospitals, and educational institutions by distinguishing efficient from inefficient units within a given set.

DEA is versatile: input and output indicators can be quantitative or qualitative, continuous or categorical, and even fuzzy or probabilistic (Chien-Ta Bruce Ho & Wu, 2009). Efficiency may be measured in absolute or relative terms. Absolute efficiency compares units against international standards, whereas relative efficiency compares them within a specific dataset. Because universal standards are often unavailable or inapplicable to local contexts, relative efficiency is generally more practical for organizational performance evaluation (Mehmet Hasan Eken & Suleyman, 2011).

For a DEA model to be valid, the decision-making units must be homogeneous—sharing similar inputs, outputs, and operating conditions. Selecting appropriate and comparable indicators is therefore crucial; merely having identical labels such as “bank” or “insurance company” does not necessarily imply homogeneity (Amaratunga et al., 2001).

Neely and Bourne (as cited in Bourne et al., 2000) identified two main reasons for the failure of performance-measurement systems:

1. Poor Design – Effective systems must begin with a clear success map outlining the organization’s strategic logic and cause-and-effect relationships.
2. Implementation Failures – Even well-designed systems can fail during execution because of political, infrastructural, or organizational challenges. Political issues arise when employees perceive performance metrics as threats rather than as improvement tools, whereas infrastructural problems stem from fragmented data systems and lack of integration.

Artley and Stroh (2001) further outlined common pitfalls in implementing measurement systems, emphasizing that organizations often underestimate the resources, time, and coordination required to sustain them effectively.

In the context of electronic commerce, performance evaluation also extends to the digital domain, where most transactions occur virtually—without face-to-face interaction—through the exchange of information over communication networks (Crede, 1999). Only the final stage, such as delivery of physical goods, requires tangible interaction. Payments in this system can be made via cash, electronic transfers, or bank cards (Vasu Deva, 2008).

Advantages of Electronic Banking

Medium-term benefits of e-banking include integration of multiple service channels, enhanced information management, broader customer reach, directing customers toward optimal service channels, and reduced operational costs (Gurau, 2002). Long-term advantages include lower transaction-processing costs, improved targeting of services to desired market segments, and increased revenue generation (Daniel, 1999).

Leading financial institutions have integrated various e-banking channels into unified systems, improving information management, customer-relationship management (CRM), and overall satisfaction (Kaplan & Norton, 1996). These improvements yield cost savings and higher profitability. However, before implementing such systems, banks must assess technical, financial, and human feasibility to ensure successful deployment (Mehmet Hasan Eken & Suleyman, 2011).

Table 2 presents a sample comparison of internet-banking usage rates among different countries (Emor, 2002).

In 2005, more than 75 percent of active companies in developed countries used at least one form of electronic-banking service (Daniel, 1999). For this reason, in most nations, the percentage of people adopting the internet and electronic banking—especially online banking—has steadily increased (Kerem et al., 2003). Another challenge is rating or risk assessment, which unfortunately is not implemented in some contexts. The lack of a legal framework for electronic banking also remains a major obstacle. In traditional transactions, paper documents not only hold value but are also legally recognized in courts (Emor, 2002).

Depending on infrastructure and market needs, electronic banking is offered in various forms, including internet banking, mobile banking and related technologies, telephone banking, fax-based banking, ATM-based banking, and POS (Point-of-Sale) terminal banking (Kerem et al., 2003).

Currently, the widespread expansion of electronic and satellite communications has profoundly influenced daily human activity. Experts continually seek to leverage modern technologies to simplify operations—allowing businesses, service organizations, and other institutions to

connect with customers quickly, efficiently, and independent of time and location. They can offer products, provide services, and even conduct buying and selling transactions virtually. One of the most recent applications of such services is the provision of banking and financial services via mobile phones (Artely & Suzanne, 2001).

Electronic Banking

To begin, we examine electronic banking and then discuss the challenges associated with it.

Electronic banking includes systems that allow customers of financial institutions to use banking services and facilities at three levels—information, communication, and transaction (Yu Zhang et al., 2012). In essence, electronic banking refers to the use of advanced software and hardware technologies based on telecommunications and networking systems for the electronic exchange of financial resources and information, eliminating the need for customers to be physically present at bank branches (Gurau, 2002).

The evolution of the banking system can be divided into four major stages. Each stage of development has enabled bank managers to minimize downtime, enhance competitiveness, and expand service delivery with greater speed, quality, accuracy, and diversity:

- *First Stage: Back-Office Automation* — This technology emerged in the 1960s, enabling the removal of paper ledgers and the daily transmission of account updates to central computers. This marked the beginning of computerization in banking, primarily focused on converting paper documents into electronic records (Mattila et al., 2002).
- *Second Stage: Front-Office Automation* — Beginning in the late 1970s, this stage allowed bank employees to continuously access customer accounts through telecommunications lines and

mainframe systems. During this period, banks relied on communication networks owned by state enterprises (Yu Zhang et al., 2012).

- *Third Stage: Connecting Customers to Accounts* — Starting in the mid-1980s, this stage allowed customers to access their accounts via telephones, ATMs, smart cards, magnetic cards, or personal computers. Customers could perform deposits, withdrawals, and fund transfers electronically. The key feature distinguishing this phase was the expansion of communication systems connecting customers directly to their accounts (Mehmet Hasan Eken & Suleyman, 2011).

- *Fourth Stage: System Integration and Full Connectivity* — The final phase began when all banking operations could be performed electronically. Both banks and customers could access accurate and real-time information, as these systems shifted from account-based to customer-based operations. This period marked true labor efficiency, as money became entirely electronic and intangible, with all interactions between banks and clients conducted through digital services (Yu Zhang et al., 2012).

The proactive and forward-looking nature of electronic banking distinguishes it from traditional banking. For instance, in 1981, ATMs accounted for only 6 percent of total cash withdrawals; this figure rose to 44 percent in 1990 and 49 percent in 1994 (Mattila et al., 2002).

According to Forrester Research (as cited in Booz-Allen & Hamilton, 1996), between 2002 and 2006, the global volume of e-commerce was expected to grow by an average of more than 58 percent annually—rising from USD 2.293 trillion in 2002 to over USD 12.837 trillion by 2006.

Internet banking is a subset of web-based banking. This approach goes beyond providing basic personal financial management; it enables a full range of retail and corporate financial services through digital communication channels (Crede, 1999).

TV-based banking is another innovative method of delivering banking services directly to customers' homes. The use of satellite systems to provide banking services through television began in some European countries, such as the United Kingdom, in 1997 (Daniel, 1999).

Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) represented the earliest practical step toward electronic banking. Although ATMs were initially viewed primarily as tools for timely cash delivery, growing competition, innovation, and changing customer needs prompted banks to revise their strategies. They began identifying challenges and restructuring their digital infrastructure to develop more efficient electronic-banking networks. Factors such as brand reputation, security, speed, social interaction, user-friendliness, cost, and flexibility in time and location became key determinants of success (Mattila et al., 2002).

As a result, banks and financial institutions continue to expand their services to gain broader commercial reach. These efforts aim to enhance profitability, attract new customers, strengthen loyalty among existing clients, and establish a foundation for new service products—while also opening new markets and increasing brand reputation. The strategic rationale behind electronic-banking development lies in maintaining market position, creating value for customers and banks, attracting more clients, responding to customer needs, improving competitiveness and efficiency, and fostering long-term customer loyalty (Mehmet Hasan Eken & Suleyman, 2011).

Challenges, Specific Risks of E-Banking Systems, DEA, and Efficient Ranking

One of the primary challenges in electronic banking involves electronic information-transfer systems, which are interactive platforms that enable the exchange of sensitive messages, texts, or files between financial institutions and users. This category includes electronic-mail systems that allow the transmission of confidential information. A bank's website that enables customers to download or submit loan applications is another example of such systems. The security of communications is a critical component of these systems. For instance, the internet is inherently insecure because data are transmitted through multiple and often untrusted networks. Security risks include data protection, confidentiality, data integrity, authentication, non-repudiation, and access-system design. To mitigate or minimize these risks, financial institutions must apply the latest technologies and international standards (Daniel, 1999).

The unique risks associated with electronic-banking channels can be categorized into six main areas. Some risks stem from the speed and scale of digital operations, while others arise from third-party dependencies or legal uncertainties. The key risk areas include feasibility analysis and strategic planning; managerial supervision and internal controls; operational procedures and policies; system and operational security; and continuous review of technological developments and capability enhancement (Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, 2003). As previously noted, electronic-banking systems enable customers of financial institutions to access banking services at three levels—information, communication, and transactions (Sokolov, 2007).

Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is a technique introduced by Charnes, Cooper, and Rhodes in 1978 for evaluating the relative efficiency of decision-making units (DMUs) using mathematical programming (Chien-Ta Bruce Ho & Wu, 2009). The term relative signifies that efficiency is determined by comparing units with each other rather than against an external standard. One of

DEA's major advantage is that it estimates a production function—a function that provides the maximum possible output for a given set of inputs, thereby allowing analysts to assess how efficiently a unit operates. In microeconomics, estimating this function is crucial, as it helps evaluate organizational performance and efficiency (Mehmet Hasan Eken & Suleyman, 2011). Although the true production function is rarely known, researchers can approximate it using various methods based on observed data. Multiple techniques exist for this estimation, and in addition to DEA, this study also considers related efficiency-analysis methods (Amaratunga et al., 2001).

In DEA, the evaluated units are divided into two groups: efficient and inefficient. Efficient units are those that achieve an efficiency score of 1, while inefficient units score below 1 and can be ranked accordingly. However, classical DEA models cannot distinguish or rank units that all have an efficiency score equal to 1 (Chien-Ta Bruce Ho & Wu, 2009).

Conceptual Framework of the Study

A review of existing literature revealed that several studies have investigated the use of the internet and telecommunications in marketing activities and have proposed models for assessing organizations' readiness to implement e-marketing (Amaratunga et al., 2001). However, few researchers have applied the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) technique to evaluate and rank the efficiency of electronic-banking systems. The only identified study in this area was conducted by Chien-Ta Bruce Ho and Desheng Dash Wu (2009), titled "Evaluating Online Banking Using DEA." In their research, they considered three input variables—equipment,

operational costs, and number of employees—and two output variables—network measures and income.

In the current study, the conceptual framework builds on that foundation and extends it by incorporating the assumption that electronic banking output—especially non-face-to-face electronic transactions—plays a central and direct role in determining the efficiency of bank branches. DEA is used as the core analytical model because it allows efficiency to be defined as a function of both input resources and output results, and because the relative nature of DEA makes it possible to identify the best-performing branches that form the efficiency frontier. Therefore, this conceptual framework positions electronic banking and digital transaction capability as key strategic drivers of organizational performance in the banking sector, and justifies the application of DEA in evaluating and ranking branches according to how well they convert controllable inputs into performance outcomes.

Research Hypotheses, Methodology, and Indicator Identification

The relationship between bank branch efficiency and electronic banking was examined using the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) method (Chien-Ta Bruce Ho & Wu, 2009). The hypotheses were analyzed through the DEA software to assess efficiency scores and performance rankings.

This study employs a descriptive-survey design and follows an applied research orientation. Both library and field research methods were used for data collection and analysis (Amaratunga et al., 2001). The statistical population consisted of all bank branches (N = 355). Using cluster random sampling, a total of 185 branches were selected for the study. To collect data and identify input and output indicators, tools such as questionnaires, interviews with bank managers, and

consultations with academic experts were used. Additionally, relevant statistical data were obtained through library research. The DEA method—a relatively modern analytical technique introduced by Charnes, Cooper, and Rhodes in 1978—was applied for data processing and analysis (Chien-Ta Bruce Ho & Wu, 2009). The spatial scope of this study included all selected bank branches, and the temporal scope covered financial data from 2007 to 2010.

As part of the implementation process, the first step involved the identification of inputs and outputs. One limitation of DEA is that the total number of input and output variables must not exceed one-third of the total number of decision-making units. Therefore, the most significant and relevant indicators were selected using the Delphi method (Mehmet Hasan Eken & Suleyman, 2011). The final selected input and output indicators for this study were as follows:

In this study, three input variables and two output variables were used to assess efficiency through the DEA model. The inputs included (X_1) equipment (vehicles, telephones, fax machines, computers, and related software), (X_2) operational costs, and (X_3) number of employees. The output indicators consisted of (Y_1) network indicators (e.g., number of electronic transactions) and (Y_2) revenue. These selected inputs and outputs represent the core controllable resources and performance results that determine branch efficiency within the scope of this research.

Hypothesis Testing

As previously noted, the study sample consisted of bank branches. Given the nature of the input variables and the greater managerial control over them, input-oriented models were employed.

To measure technical efficiency, two main Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) models—CCR

and BCC—were applied, representing constant returns to scale (CRS) and variable returns to scale (VRS) conditions, respectively (Chien-Ta Bruce Ho & Wu, 2009). By solving these models, several efficiency-related indicators were obtained, including technical-efficiency scores, reference sets, reference-unit weights, optimal input and output values, and auxiliary variables under both CRS and VRS assumptions. All computations were carried out using EMS software (Mehmet Hasan Eken & Suleyman, 2011).

Through the DEA method, an efficiency score is derived—a highly suitable metric in economics for evaluating organizational performance. This approach provides a realistic assessment by identifying a subset of decision-making units (DMUs) as efficient and constructing an efficiency frontier from them. This frontier serves as the benchmark against which the performance of all other units is compared (Amaratunga et al., 2001). A key feature of DEA is that evaluation is based on comparative performance among units, rather than on any predefined external standard. The technique also supports model-based simulation, enabling the identification of improvement strategies to enhance efficiency and resource allocation.

In this study, an input-oriented technical-efficiency model was used. The principal evaluation criteria included factors associated with the procurement process—such as the allocated operational budget, the number of qualified personnel, and the availability of equipment (e.g., vehicles and communication devices)—which collectively represent critical resources required for effective organizational operations. The analysis covered 50 bank branches, evaluated using DEA software. To improve precision, branches were classified into five groups based on the similarity of their customer bases. Each branch's efficiency was then assessed using three input variables—equipment, personnel, and operational expenses—and two output variables—income and network measures (e.g., the number of electronic transactions).

Using the DEA models, efficiency scores were computed for all groups. Branches that achieved the highest level of efficiency and formed the efficiency frontier were assigned a score of 100, representing full efficiency. Branches that did not meet this level were considered inefficient and received proportionally lower scores based on their distance from the frontier. Moreover, efficient branches were further ranked according to their relative contribution to the efficiency frontier, with top-performing branches earning scores exceeding 100. Inefficient branches, which did not influence the frontier's formation, retained their original scores. This ranking approach effectively differentiates priority levels among efficient branches and provides practical insight into performance benchmarking.

Figure 1

Efficiency Ranking of the Most Efficient Bank Branches

Source: Author's own work.

As illustrated, the most efficient bank branches were compared with one another, revealing that the Six-District branch achieved the highest efficiency score of 0.917, making it the most efficient branch overall.

The accompanying chart demonstrates the correlation between each performance indicator and overall branch efficiency, allowing for a clear understanding of how individual variables influence efficiency levels.

The following table presents the correlation coefficients between input and output indicators and branch efficiency across the five branch groups.

Table 3.

Correlation Between Input and Output Indicators and Efficiency

Index	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Average
Operational Costs	0.04	-0.05	0.30	0.27	0.43	0.20
Equipment	0.30	-0.50	0.06	0.35	0.33	0.11
Personnel	0.50	0.47	0.20	0.37	0.41	0.38
Income	0.30	0.15	0.3	0.37	0.41	0.31
Network Indicators	0.87	0.68	0.57	0.56	0.51	0.64

Source: Author’s own work.

The indexes used in this study included operational costs, equipment, personnel, income, and network indicators. As shown in Table 3, the two output variables—income (average $r = 0.31$) and especially network indicators (average $r = 0.64$)—reported the highest positive correlations with branch efficiency. In contrast, the input variables such as equipment (average $r = 0.11$) and operational costs (average $r = 0.20$) demonstrated weaker relationships. These results clearly

indicate that branches with higher levels of electronic/non-face-to-face transactions (network indicators) tend to be substantially more efficient overall compared to branches that rely less on digital transaction channels.

Analysis of Findings

This study examined whether there is a significant relationship between home and office electronic banking and branch profitability. To ensure a more precise efficiency analysis, branches were grouped into five categories based on the similarity of their customer numbers. Using the DEA (Data Envelopment Analysis) method, three input variables—equipment, personnel, and operating costs—and two output variables—income and network measures (number of electronic/non-in-person transactions)—were used to assess branch efficiency.

The results comparing inefficient branches with the most efficient ones in each group show that the two output components—income and network measures (electronic transactions)—were the main factors contributing to inefficiency, with electronic transactions being the most influential variable. The correlation analysis also revealed a strong, positive relationship between output components and overall branch efficiency. Branches with higher levels of these two components, especially electronic transactions, achieved greater efficiency.

Thus, it can be confidently stated that electronic banking increases operational efficiency and ultimately boosts profitability. In addition, efficient branches had lower operating costs than inefficient ones, confirming that the implementation of electronic banking helps reduce operational expenses.

Conclusion

The results of this research indicate that the main reasons for efficiency in the most successful branches were the high volume of electronic transactions and the resulting reduction in operational costs. Therefore, to enhance the efficiency of less efficient branches and turn them into efficient ones, it is essential to (1) increase electronic transaction activity in branches according to their potential, and (2) control operational costs when implementing programs to expand electronic banking. The potential of each branch refers to the gap between an inefficient branch and its reference (efficient) branch; closing this gap transforms an inefficient branch into an efficient one.

One effective method for estimating the efficiency frontier and measuring efficiency is Linear Programming, which does not assume a specific functional form for the frontier. This method, known as Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), aims to compare and evaluate several homogeneous decision-making units (DMUs) with identical types of inputs and outputs but different quantities of input consumption and output production. As a fundamental management principle, organizational performance must be measurable. The existence or absence of an effective performance-evaluation system directly affects the organization's survival. As the saying goes, what cannot be measured cannot be effectively managed. Organizations must adopt scientific performance-evaluation models to assess their efforts and outcomes accurately.

One of the most effective tools to achieve this is Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). In this study, several bank branches were analyzed. Due to limitations on the number of input and output variables relative to the number of decision-making units, some variables were selected through the Delphi method based on their priority and importance. Given that inputs are controllable by management, the DEA models CCR, BCC, and NIRS were used to measure

technical efficiency, scale efficiency, and returns to scale. These models also provided strategies for improving the performance of inefficient units.

Finally, the branches that achieved an efficiency score equal to one in the CCR model were identified as fully efficient units, and among them, the Six-District branch was determined to be the most super-efficient branch.

References

- Abbasi, J., Kavousi, A., & Esmaeili, Z. (2012). Evaluation of factors affecting brand equity in the banking industry. *Journal of Industrial Strategic Management*, 8(24), 90–99.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17497410>
- Amaratunga, D., Baldry, D., & Marjan, S. (2001). Process improvement through performance measurement: The balanced scorecard methodology. *Work Study*, 50(5), 179–188.
- Artely, & Suzanne. (2001). Umbilical cord blood banking: Implication for perinatal care providers. *SOGE* (156), 9–10.
- Basel Committee on Banking Supervision. (2003). *Risk management principles for electronic banking*.
- Blount, Y., & Castleman, T. (2002). Implementation of electronic commerce and human resource management strategies in an Australian retail banking context. *COLLECTeR Conference Proceedings*.
- Booz Allen & Hamilton. (1996). *Internet banking: A survey of current and future development*.
- Bourne, M. C. S., Mills, J. F., Wilcox, M., Neely, A. D., & Platts, K. W. (2000). Designing, implementing and updating performance measurement systems. *International Journal of Production & Operations Management*, 20(7), 754–771.
- Chien-Ta, B. H., & Desheng, D. W. (2009). Online banking performance evaluation using data envelopment analysis and principal component analysis. *Computers and Operations Research*, 36(6), 1835–1842.

- Crede, A. (1999). Electronic commerce and the banking industry: The requirement and opportunities for new payment systems using the internet. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 1(3), 18.
- Daniel, E. (1999). Provision of electronic banking in the UK and the Republic of Ireland. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 17(2), 72–82.
- Deva, V. (2008). *E-banking*. Commonwealth Publishers.
- Eken, M. H., & Suleyman. (2011). Measuring bank branch performance using data envelopment analysis (DEA): The case of bank branches. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(3), 889–901.
- Emor. (2002). *E-monitoring report (March–May)*. [in Estonian]
- Esmaeili, Z. (2009a). *Financial services marketing*. Department of Education, Educational Center of Private Banking.
- Esmaeili, Z. (2009b). *Managerial strategies*. Department of Education, Educational Center of Private Banking.
- Esmaeili, Z. (2010a). *Examining the impact of selected service marketing-mix elements (7Ps) on brand equity in the banking industry* [Master's thesis].
- Esmaeili, Z. (2010b, November 26). Investigating the impact of selected marketing mix elements on brand equity: The case of the banking industry. In *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Financial Services Marketing*. Financial Services Marketing Center.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17497345>

- Esmaeili, Z. (2011a). Studying the relationship between organizational factors with debt collections of banks. *Market Engineering Development Journal*.
- Esmaeili, Z. (2011b). The effect of marketing mix on brand equity in banking industry. *Market Engineering Development Journal*.
- Esmaeili, Z., Akbari, E., & Dehpoor, A. (2012, October). Evaluating the relationship between bank loan interest rates, delinquent accounts, and the effective role of marketing. *Fourth International Conference on Banking Services Marketing*.
- Amini, S.M., Esmaeili, Z. (2013). Effective factors in appointment and selecting bank managers using fuzzy TOPSIS model development. *Market Engineering Development Journal*.
- Gurau, C. (2002). E-banking in transition economies: The case of Romania. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, 6(4), 362–379.
- Kaplan, R. S., & Norton, D. P. (1996). Linking the balanced scorecard to strategy. *California Management Review*, 39(1), 38–41.
- Kerem, K., Luataik, O., Sorg, M., & Vensel, V. (2003). The development of e-banking in an EU candidate country: An Estonian case. *Proceedings of the International Atlantic Economic Society Conference*, Vienna, March 11–17.
- Mattila, M., Karjaluoto, H., & Pento, T. (2002). Internet banking adoption among mature customers: Early majority or laggards? *Journal of Services Marketing*, 17.
- Pohjola, M. (2002). The new economy: Facts, impacts and policies. *Information Economics and Policy*, 14, 133–144.

Seyed Hosseini, M., & Esmaeili, Z. (2013). Reviewing services quality in banking industry. *Market Engineering Development Journal*.

Shemirani, H., & Esmaeili, Z. (2014). *Evaluation of bank branch efficiency using data envelopment analysis (DEA) software. Market Engineering Development Journal*, (92).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17537685>

Sokolov, D. (2007). E-banking: Risk management practices of the Estonian banks. *Tallinn School of Economics and Business Administration Working Papers*.

Verma, S. B., Gupta, S. K., & Sharma, M. K. (2007). *E-banking and development of banks*. Deep & Deep Publications Pvt. Ltd.

Zhang, Y., Chen, K. L., Lee, H., & Yang, J. (2012). Adoption of online banking features by financial intermediaries. *International Journal of Electronic Finance*, 6(3–4), 219–238.